

HOW TO TEACH ENGLISH YOUNG LEARNERS

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***Abstract** Teaching language to old learners is different from teaching Language to young learners. Young learners have certain characteristics which are Different from old learners so those influence their acquiring a foreign language. Teaching foreign language is easy if we understand the rules well. The rules are Understanding characteristics of our students, mastering some suitable methods, and Choosing suitable material. Young learners have certain characteristic Distinguishing to the older learners. Related to the certain characteristics, the Teacher must understand to differentiate the method they use in teaching English as A foreign language to the young learners. To empower the teaching, the teacher must Master the material well.*

***Key Words.** Teaching English, Teaching learners, young learners, language, Listening skills, speaking skill, writing skill, teacher education, teacher Educator,creative teacher talk.*

This article explores the demanding and complex nature of teaching English To young learners. The article begins with the challenges of the early childhood Classroom, then goes on to say that underestimating language teaching in elementary Education can seriously affect the confidence and effectiveness of primary teachers. It is a common question that English for young learners is a simple problem that Does not require advanced language skills or in-depth knowledge of educational Abilities and pedagogy. In this article, the role of children's literature in teacher Training is highlighted and the relevance of high quality linguistic input is discussed. In addition, the availability of in-service and targeted teachers, as well as teacher Trainers with the required expertise, will be discussed. Finally, the role of the teacher in providing language skills to young learners through creative storytelling and Teacher conversation is explored.

How To Teach English, Teaching Young Learners. Learning is fun! TEYL Or Teaching English to Young Learners refers to a more specialized area Of teaching EnglishAlso, and this is ... students. Younger which deals with.only English s good to speak'important, itYoung children who are learning Languages are very proficient at working out what languages people speak and will Switch automatically to what is appropriate. Even though you may understand the Child's mother tongue (MT) and be able to respond, unless it's an emergency you Should speak only in English with the child (while at the same time allowing the Child to speak their MT).

Teaching English as a second language for beginners is a challenging task for Anyone. No matter what your background, or experience level, you will encounter Constant new challenges when teaching English as a second language. Like teaching Other subjects, you'll find that every student learns differently. At the same time, Depending on the primary language of each student, you'll face new challenges Unique to that language. However, with some work and knowledge, you'll be able To gain the skills you need to teach English as a second language to beginners learner. Languages has some skills to understand, listening skills, speaking skill,reading Skill and writing skill.

Those skills have their own characteristics to be understood and to mastered. Mastering all those skills needs some certain method too and but we can learn them As step by step. Every language teacher should understand well related to the skills When they are teaching language. It influences teaching the language. As a teacher Should understand well which skill the students should learn first how to teach each Skill and how to the teach skill and what the characters of the language learners. When the teacher understand those well, it will be easy to recognize the learners.,to Choose the suitable method and to find the suitable materials .

Teaching foreign languages are different from teaching first language, even Though some of the orders are same. Before we teach second language of course we have to understand the first language then before we learn foreign language we have To understand second language.

One recommendation for any young learner teacher is to make and use lots of Flashcards in your classes. If I had been told about using flashcards in class before Teaching children, it would have made my life a lot easier. There are some great Games you could include in class with flashcards and I would urge any new teacher To do this. It does take some preparation to compile your own flashcards: you have To print them out, maybe colour them, and laminate them so you can reuse them. Teachers should: Use culturally compatible instruction to build a bridge between Home and school. Make the norms and expectations of the classroom clear and Explicit. Activate existing background knowledge and build new background Knowledge to increase comprehension.

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